

Web Publications for Digitized Archives

An investigation in user requirements and technical possibilities

Table of Content

3	1 Introduction
7	2 User Research
10	3 Demonstrator
18	4 Fit-gap analysis
26	5 Cost-benefit analysis
28	6 Further research
31	7 Conclusion

1

Introduction

1 Introduction

In the project Web Publications for digitized archives, we investigated if and how emerging technologies for digital publishing, could also benefit the usability of digitized documents. The National Library (KB) and the National Archives of the Netherlands (NA) both have large collections of digitized material, which we think can be of interest to much more people than those currently visiting us. This could be partially because online we cannot show contemporary materials, because of copyright and privacy regulations. However another reason could be that the way in which we make materials available, does not meet the needs of the modern digital user. We have already identified three types of usage that have developed in recent years:

- 1 Users do not exclusively browse and read through documents themselves, but increasingly use computers to do this. This enables the user to quickly analyze huge amounts of documents ('distant reading') before deciding to read and annotate texts themselves ('close reading').
- 2 Users with reading disabilities expect digital services to be accessible to them. European legislation will extend to digital content (such as e-books) in 2025, making it increasingly desirable to make existing content more accessible.
- 3 Users are increasingly using mobile phones and tablets to access digital services. To accommodate these smaller screens and use on the move, it is desirable that the presentation/view of the document can be adapted.

At present, the formats in which the materials are being offered, PDF among others, are often static formats. We felt that another format, namely that of Web Publications could perhaps better fit the needs of our primary user groups. This project aimed to take stock of the needs of our primary user groups and to explore if the web publications format could possibly fit those needs. Our project team consists of members from the National Library, the National Archives, the TU Delft Future Libraries Lab, and the agency Van Leeuwen & Van Leeuwen.

In all three new cases we identified earlier, we realize these are difficult to address using traditional formats such as PDF. Therefore, it was decided to look at the latest developments in digital publishing. One potential direction where digital publishing could be going, is using Web technology not only for online publishing, but also for off-line documents and even print. When talking about Web Publications in this document, we do not mean 'any document published on the web' but much more specific 'digital publications designed to become part of the World Wide Web'. This concept has been described in "Web Publications for the Open Web Platform: Vision And Technical Challenges".¹ And though current adaption is still limited, the standardization that led to the success of the World Wide Web, could help the traditional publishing industry enormously, especially when making the step to multi-channel publishing.

In this research we studied whether these new emerging standards could also help with 're-publishing' digitized content from archives. What would be the benefits for the user? How to transform existing sources? Do we have all standards and tools needed to do this? And what would such a transformation cost?

So what are Web Publications and why do we think that this format will improve how we make digitized materials available? To answer that question we have to go back a bit and look at the alternatives. If we compare the World Wide Web with earlier networked information resources, we notice a couple of major advantages:

- All resources can be addressed directly by an URL and accessed in a standardized way (HTTP)
- All resources are formatted in one document language (HTML) so a user needs only one application, namely a web browser, to view it.
- Web resources are relatively open, which makes it easier to interact with. For example one could query for just a part of a web page (like just one image) or change the complete page rendering (to view on a small screen size like that of a mobile phone)
- Because of this standardization other large scale services were realized (like Google Search) and we expect many more to come.

Many documents that existed before the Web are formatted in for example proprietary formats such as Word (.doc or .docx) or PDF. These formats all need proprietary software for viewing, interacting and editing. Many are closed (can only be accessed as a whole, not in parts), and do not provide possibilities to have document elements linked directly from external (web) resources.

E-books, more specifically the ePub format, have been built with web technologies (HTML/CSS). The Web Publication concept proposes to go one step further, and make it possible to integrate e-books fully with the existing World Wide Web. Instead of viewing books as isolated items, publications would become parts of a much larger information fabric and make use of all services that are developed for the web.

This 'dream' to connect the information from current isolated resources into one connected web, was expressed as: "a fully native representation of documents within the Open Web Platform. Web publications can be packaged and they can be portable. Web publications work online or offline. Web publications can be accessible, linkable, and annotatable."²

If we compare current digitized books with current e-books, we notice that e-books are much easier to use for most consumers. E-books can be adapted for easy reading on different formats, are portable (for off-line use) and allow to easy search.

The formats that we currently use for digitized documents are more 'exotic'. OCR output formats like METS³/ALTO⁴, Page XML⁵ or hOCR⁶, are hardly practical for consumers, so if consumers want to download resources and work with these, we always need to convert these first. These conversions work mostly one way: we can produce a file (like PDF) but connecting back to the source (to propagate corrections or annotations) is not possible. Using HTML (and other web technologies) should minimize the need for conversions and keep information much more connected.

Another format to look at would be PDF. PDF started before the web and originally was only focused to interchange information in a more reliable way as described in the Camelot paper.⁷ However, even after 20 years, the format is not considered optimal for online reading as pointed out by several studies such as the study by Norman and Nilsen.⁸ New developments by Adobe are aiming for better accessibility (PDF/UA) and usability (Liquid), but we noted some other disadvantages:

- PDF is much more closed. (though developers outside Adobe work on viewers and tools, the development community is way smaller than the millions of people who know how to work with HTML)
- The 'searchable text' in a PDF is hard to access and or correct. Exchange of corrections with external sources is not implemented.
- Annotations can only be defined locally: these cannot be shared with other people that have the same document
- Linking to specific texts in a PDF from other documents /websites is not implemented.

In this report, we will present the different activities that we have done during this project. Chapter 2 will report on the user research that was conducted, chapter 3 on the demonstrator that was built, chapter 4 on the fit-gap analysis, and chapter 5 on the cost-benefit analysis. The user research and the cost-benefit analysis are summarized versions of longer reports that are available. The links to those reports are available in the footnotes accompanying the relevant chapters. At the end of the report, we will expand on what we think needs further research and our conclusions.

2

User research

2 User research

2.1 Setup

As mentioned before, this project aimed to research the needs of the primary usergroup concerning digitized materials. What are functionalities they want to have available in the future? For this project, our primary usergroup was identified as academic participants coming mainly from humanistic backgrounds. This group are the most likely to make (extensive) use of the digitized materials from the KB and the NA.

Before we conducted an extensive user research, we decided upon a brief set of probing survey questions which would allow us to gather some basic information from academic users about specific types of interactions they have with digitized documents, particularly those held in the KB. As of 30 June 2021 there were 23 responses. Participants were recruited from professional networks, in particular those relating to Digital Humanities, as well as personal and professional contacts of the Web Publications team.

For the more extensive user research, a total of 10 people were interviewed. It should be highlighted that, because the number of participants was small, the results are therefore exploratory. Our main purpose here was to highlight prospective areas for further study and development. Most of these were full-time researchers in fields such as history, journalism, linguistics, and stylometry. The sample represented a wide range of academic experience – one participant having fewer than two years of experience and eight stating to have 20+ years of experience. Furthermore, their experience working with digital tools was diverse, ranging from simple web research, to research conducted through advanced computational research tools, image recognition or contribution to the generation of specialized tools. The participants were primarily Dutch and working at institutions within the Netherlands.

During the interview sessions, participants were asked to walk through a series of topics on a Miro board. Topics included habits involving usage of digitized documents held in libraries and archives, but participants were free to deviate from this schema to elaborate on topics they deemed important or relevant to their usage of digitized documents. Participants were encouraged to actively edit the board, though in most cases, for reasons of comfort with the Miro tool, members of the design team annotated the boards while participants spoke. Two initial sessions were done with members of the Web Publications team to test and refine the board content and length. Participants were self-selecting from those who indicated interest when filling in the survey.

2.2 Results

In order to get insights into the needs of the community, we wanted to first understand how people are using digitized materials now and what the issues are that they face. As discussed in the setup, we set up a survey prior to the more extensive user research (the interviews) to be filled in. Some preliminary takeaways from the survey include:

- Academics utilize webdocs¹⁰ for a variety of purposes, from the highly technical (training handwritten text recognition models) to uses beyond the academy (just for fun). Designs should reflect this multiplicity of use.

- Academic users self-identify as being part of a wide variety of disciplines: e.g. art history, media, AI, genetics.
- Access to images and 'texts' appears to be equally valuable.
- A majority of respondents (18/23) state that they use library materials at multiple stages of a research process.
- A small portion of respondents (4/23) use annotation markup tools, and slightly more (7/23) feed webdocs into scripting packages for various purposes.
- All respondents (23/23) indicated that easy access was moderately to extremely important for webdocs.
- Multiple individual wishes are given in the open response sections, some of which could bear following up:
 - More digitized materials (e.g. dissertations)
 - 'Easier access', including e.g. not having to sign contracts to download datasets
 - Improved OCR (presumably for searchability)

Using the more extensive interview, we gained more insight concerning preferences among the participants. Most commonly used by the participants were manuscripts, early printed books, newspapers, and letters. An important finding from the interviews was that the participants indeed feel that they have limited possibilities when using digitized materials and that some even feel forced to create these possibilities themselves. Wishes included possibilities such as collaboration with others, granular citation, and personalized workspaces. Three themes are central amongst the wishes and needs of the participants: access, quality, and connections. More details on the user research can be found in "Summary of Insights from WebDocs interviews"⁹

2.3 Conclusion

The user research was conducted twofold. The short survey gave us insights that were subsequently repeated during the extensive interviews. The wishes and needs of the participants can be placed into three broad themes: access, quality, and connections. Currently, people are working around the existing limited possibilities offered by downloading all the materials they need and creating code themselves. In the future, we imagine that Web Publications can improve the user experience for the participants and offer more possibilities.

3

Demonstrator

3 Demonstrator

3.1 Introduction

The demonstrator developed in this project offers users the possibility to see a selection of publications in the form of a Web Publication, in a web environment. This environment offers functionalities to the user such as navigation, annotation, granular bookmarking, reading text out aloud and translation.

The initial idea was to make this demonstrator part of the 'KB atelier', physically situated between the buildings of KB and NA. This would allow us to interactively engage not only the interviewees, but also the general public in our project. The Covid-19 pandemic made this idea impossible. Project members were asked to work from home and for long stretches of time, there were hardly any visitors in the buildings.

Our alternative was to make the demonstrator versions available online, so that the interviewers and interviewees could use it during the user research. And to make the demonstrator more easily available to a larger, online, audience after the project ended.

This change of plans also resulted in a name for the final demonstrator. In a physical setting, we could have given a verbal explanation and more context about the demonstrator. This was also still possible in the interviews. But in an online setting for the general public, we felt we needed to provide this kind of information with the demonstrator. This requirement also introduced the need for a name for this demonstrator, as 'Web Publications demonstrator' was too vague and uninviting. Several brainstorm sessions led to the name 'SamePage' for our demonstrator.¹¹

3.2 Publications

Alice in Wonderland
(Lewis Carroll)

Max Havelaar
(Multatuli)

With both KB and NA as stakeholders in this project, we added digitised material from both organisations to the demonstrator. KB already had publications available in formats close to Web Publications (e.g. ePub3), and with transcriptions of the digitised text. We therefore decided to add two copyright free documents from the KB to the initial demonstrator: Alice in Wonderland (Lewis Carroll) and Max Havelaar (Multatuli).

Notariële akten van notarissen te Haarlem (Nieuw Notarieel Archief Haarlem) 1887-1925, nummer archiefinventaris 1972, inventarisnummer 466, scannummer 0139.

Later in the project, we were able to use the results of the project “De IJsborg zichtbaar maken” that NA worked on together with Noord-Hollands Archief, using the international transcription platform Transkribus.¹² This project added the results of handwritten text recognition (HTR, in the form of XML) to digitised archival material. We were especially happy that our colleague Liesbeth Keijser of NA’s Digitisation department informed us, that this IJsborg contained a document with references to Eduard Douwes Dekker, who wrote Max Havelaar using the pen name Multatuli. Similar to Alice in Wonderland and Max Havelaar, we could now add digitised archival material with a transcription to SamePage.

3.3 Initial functionalities

The initial demonstrator – not yet SamePage – provided the following functionalities on top of the layers with the scan and the transcription:

- Navigation
- Fixed vs. reflow view, both with the option to zoom in or out
- Simple text search
- Turning on or off the layers of the Web Publication (i.e. showing or hiding the scan).

Screenshot demonstrator

3.4 The initial demonstrator: technical details

3.4.1 The documents

When we started with the development of the initial demonstrator, we had ePub and XML documents. They needed to be cleared of all additional information such as footnotes, ends notes and other content elements which were not determined as core content for the demonstrator experiments. To be able to have a proper basic content layer we checked the underlying code for any faults and irregularities.

A major challenge was that many old documents which use hand written or hand set typography are almost impossible to reproduce in HTML without many manual adjustments and additional code. If, e.g., a text is fully justified the text is differently set in HTML than in the printed document. This can be because the original printed document is hand set or the original software used slightly different rules to render a justified text. This seems like small details, but this can cause lines of text to be on completely different parts in the HTML document.

Another limitation is the difference in hierarchy between XML and HTML. In HTML, an element has to be closed before you can start another element. For example if you have a paragraph (`<p>`) inside a page the paragraph has to be closed (`</p>`) before you can close the page. To have paragraphs running into another page you need to have additional Javascript as HTML by default cannot support this behavior.

As a result, we needed to write additional code for the limitation of HTML. And most of these limitations are not with Web Publications, but with HTML.

The user research was conducted twofold. The short survey gave us insights that were subsequently repeated during the extensive interviews. The wishes and needs of the participants can be placed into three broad themes: access, quality, and connections. Currently, people are working around the existing limited possibilities offered by downloading all the materials they need and creating code themselves. In the future, we imagine that Web Publications can improve the user experience for the participants and offer more possibilities.

3.4.2 Demonstrator functionality

The basic default Web Publications specification which is available from W3C is limited at the moment. As there is little off-the-shelf Web Publication software, a lot of the functionality we developed ourselves, such as annotations, translation, audio, HTML editor, scan editor. We also got our inspiration from ePub developments or existing experiments in other projects.

3.5 Samepage

As a result of the user research and Van Leeuwen & Van Leeuwen's experience in developing the initial demonstrator, we were able to prioritise which functionalities we could add to the final demonstrator, then coined SamePage. This prioritisation had always been foreseen and was required, because the project did not have the running time or budget to accommodate all wished for user requirements. We therefore, as a project team, prioritised those functionalities that were mentioned most by the users and were implementable within the bounds of the project. These added functionalities are:

- Create, update and delete local (private) or remote (published) Web Publications
- HTML editor (to edit the transcription, stored as HTML)
- Scan editor (to crop, rotate or zoom the scan, change the brightness, etc.)
- Fixed vs. reflow view with the option to link the displayed views
- Annotate (add annotations to selected text)
- Bookmark (add bookmarks to selected text – 'granular citation')
- Named Entities (link named entities to external thesauri, vocabulary, etc.)
- Translation (add a translated version of the publication as a layer)
- Audio (add an audio version of the publication as a layer)

Screenshot SamePage

The SamePage demonstrator and video will remain available after the project has ended via samepagedemo.com.

SamePage was developed when the user research had finished and was used for fit-gap analysis and cost-benefit analysis purposes: what does it cost to add layers to Web Publications and develop certain functionalities in SamePage? Furthermore, SamePage can be used as a publicly available Web Publication demonstrator and is foreseen as a tool for discussing Web Publication (im)possibilities in future projects.

3.6 SamePage: technical details

3.6.1 The documents

In order to use the documents from the initial document in SamePage, we had to rewrite translation scripts to translate XML documents into HTML Web Publication documents. For Alice in Wonderland we now used an ePub which was created by an external party to show the possibility of fixed layout in ePub. This Alice in Wonderland document has per single line additional code to make it look like the original scan. We could copy this ePub fixed layout variant over to Web Publications, but still it needed additional adjustments to make it fully functional in the SamePage demonstrator. This Alice in Wonderland document is not fitting the goal of the Web Publications format as we had envisioned it: a clean original HTML source without any additional code to make it work as digital twin of the original scan.

In our project, we focused mostly on text only documents. For text only documents Web Publication is a reasonable fit. Here we learned how close we could emulate the original scan with HTML without the need for much additional code. As Web Publications is still very much under developed we implemented some things that are not yet part of Web Publications in its current form. Things such as annotations, audio and named entity recognition had to be incorporated into the Web Publications format. The difficulty was to research and test which form for these additional functionalities which are not (yet) part of the Web Publications format was the best fit.

3.6.2 SamePage functionality

SamePage used the W3C Open Web Platform standards HTML, CSS and JavaScript. We needed a little bit of PHP to make a secure connection between SamePage and certain cloud services (e.g. for translation and versioning). For the real time translation services we used Microsoft Azure Cloud translation services. For the overall development of the online snippet / versioning functionality we used Google Firebase services. These services can be changed into other services if needed.

3.6.3 SamePage findings

We learned a lot about translating documents to Web Publication documents. There are still challenges to overcome. But the main challenge lies with the usability of Web Publications, i.e. the functionality built around Web Publication documents. This challenge is probably unique for each new application, it is difficult to implement as a one-size-fits-all for every organization. Also, many of the functionalities now offered are not necessarily something only Web Publications can offer. One of the unique things Web Publications do offer is its transparent and scalable nature. Because all the separate elements (text, manifest, images, audio, TOC, etc.) are stored separately in an open structure, it is easy to use them for deep research and analysis. But we acknowledge that with the right tools much of this transparency can also be offered via other means.

3.7 Lessons learned from SamePage

In this section, we present the most important lessons learned from developing SamePage. These lessons have been used in the formation of our fit-gap analysis.

- For many types of text analysis such as indexing for search, it is sufficient if words are recognized separately. However, certain types of analysis, for example language analysis, machine translation or speech synthesis may require the recognition of whole 'sentences', 'paragraphs' and 'chapters'. Desirable is a way to redefine regions within existing OCR to include 'sentences', 'paragraphs' and 'chapters'.
- To be able to transform documents properly, it is necessary to agree on the correct definitions for the various elements such as headings, sentences, footnotes, etc. In TEI, PAGE, DAISY, HTML definitions overlap but are not equal. Very specific definitions and enrichments could also be stored in an extra 'layer' on top of the original clean document for flexibility and continuity.
- For linking annotations, enrichments in pieces of text and/or images, these need to be provided with an identifier. Annotation (also on the web) has been discussed for a long time, but has not yet led to widely accepted and implemented standards. To keep the source material clean, these identifiers must be kept separate from the source. 'Canonical Fragment Identifiers' are possible, but within ePub they have been abandoned for being too complex.
- In the SamePage demonstrator, we are currently using paragraph numbering in combination with text fragments. This possibility is only not fully applicable to the scans, where coordinates should rather be considered.
- Manifestos are practical for defining the relationships between elements. They can be used to group elements (e.g. headings, texts and images to an article or chapter, even if they are on other pages). It can also be used to specify a reading order. The idea of grouping text elements in the code (with divisions) is less flexible and will be difficult to maintain if versioning will be implemented in the future.
- A layer concept offers great flexibility to keep enrichments for different purposes and from different users separate from the original content. Although layers remind us of a canvas where relations are defined by coordinates, we can also think of defining relations by their identifiers. As we know from ePub and DAISY in which text and audio are linked by means of a SMIL file. Audio, translations or other representations can be similar linked as 'layers' in a manifest json file.
- A strong point of the Web Publications concept is that document components, such as personal annotations, audio or translations, can be kept separate, but remain combinable with the original at all times. This open structure also makes it possible to retrieve the document components separately without having to receive the whole document.
- As Web Publications is a new concept and very similar to other formats such as ePub it is not being implemented on large scale yet. Many experiments and discoveries with ePub will have to be rediscovered with Web Publications. Of course many lessons learned from ePub can be taken into consideration when developing Web Publications further.

- HTML is often seen as a less mature and extensive format for documents than XML, but HTML is web native and easier human-readable. A lot of work still has to be done to identify all missing elements in HTML that are necessary for HTML (and thus Web Publications) to be a fully functional replacement.

4

Fit-gap analysis

4 Fit-gap analysis

4.1 Structural requirements

From the W3C Web Publications specification, our knowledge and experience, desk research and experiments it became clear that in an ideal Web Publication:

- The text representation contains words, sentences and/or paragraphs as structural elements, instead of unrelated text strings
- Text and other page elements are classified in a way these map directly to WCAG page structures
- Text elements are serialized to provide 'anchors' for annotations and other forms of linking
- The reading order is made explicit (using either serialization or a manifest)
- An explicit Table of Contents is present (which partially can be generated from headings, but might also need some manual work, like adding 'editorial' headings for special pages like a colophon)
- Illustrations are individually labelled, accessible and should preferably have a text description
- Other non-text elements like math formulas or music notation are represented in a proper format (like MathML or Music XML)
- Tabular data can be represented as standardized data sets
- Text can be styled in a way that it resembles the original well enough to make visual comparison with the scanned image feasible

4.2 Structural requirements

Based on the input of the users that were interviewed, combined with the structural requirements mentioned before, we made a list of functionalities that users most often ask for. This list is not meant to be exhaustive, but it does contain the most high-priority requirements, enabling us and future project to prioritize what to work on. In the next sections, we discuss the implications of these requirements.

The requirements are, in no particular order:

- 1 Transfer of reading experience into digital tools
- 2 Personalized work spaces
- 3 Reliable search
- 4 Compare text and scan
- 5 Improve text

- 6 Adaptable presentation
- 7 Reading text aloud
- 8 Explicit navigation structure
- 9 Reading and storing documents offline
- 10 Making annotations
- 11 Granular citation
- 12 Perform text analysis
- 13 Automatic translation
- 14 Link fragments in related documents together

4.3 Implications of requirements

For each of the items from the previous section, we looked into detail what these would require of a document format, and to what extent these requirements can be met with current or future standards.

4.3.1 Transfer of reading experience into digital tools

As our interviewed users explained, resources carry with them more information than text and images. Some characteristics of the physical document are harder to view or experience in the digitized versions of resources.

Our analysis is that Web Publications as a concept or format do not provide access to the original text or image. But what Web Publications does offer, is access to a connected presentation of resources – the scan, the transcriptions and/or other document ‘layers’. The fact that Web Publications use open web technology also increases the user’s experience when compared to e.g. only having the scan available.

4.3.2 Personalized work spaces

On almost the other end of the spectrum of the user experience (when compared to having only an original document available in a reading room), lies the requirement to have a personalized work space. This electronic work space should have not only those (parts of) resources that are relevant to the user, but also provide highly personalized tools for doing research. Flexible notebook-like solutions such as Jupyter notebooks spring to mind.¹³ Also, the CLARIAH research infrastructure¹⁴ might eventually provide this type of personalized work space. What such a work space might look like can be seen in the ‘mock-up’ in the report Insights from WebDocs interviews.

Our analysis is that personalized work spaces are not a requirement for Web Publications, but for the platform or environment in which they are used. Our project provided sketches of what such an environment might look like. We also provided a demonstrator that can be used as a source of inspiration for the development of such environments.

4.3.3 Reliable search

When printed documents are digitized, manual transcriptions can be made, or OCR (Optical Character Recognition) and HTR (Handwritten text Recognition) are used to recognize the text from the scanned images. The results are stored in files, accompanying the scans. Due to the complex nature of this work, there could be errors both in characters or words, but also in document structures. Given the huge amount of pages processed, a balance always needs to be found between quality and costs. Errors in the OCR process affect usability of the digital text, in particular for discovery (e.g. full-text search). A number of ongoing efforts address this issue from different angles, and more will continue in the near future (cf. Smith & Cordell 2018).¹⁵ Our primary contribution to improving the OCR process at scale within this project is the prototype feature allowing users to emend text (and formatting) on the fly.

E.g., if a word has a transcription error, such as “Eduard Douwer Dekker” as an erroneous transcription of “Eduard Douwes Dekker”, that word will not be present in the search index. First of all, the user will not know from the index that the word “Douwes” is present in the document – you don’t know what is missing. Also, even if the user were to know that the word is present in the document, the exact word “Douwes” would not be found. Smart, concept or semantic search techniques can be used to find possible matches, but unless improvements are made to the text, the word itself will still not be part of the search space. Not all smart search techniques (such as regular expression pattern matching) are easy to learn for everyone. And smart search may result in the over-generation of hits. For “Douwer” could correctly be matched with “Douwes”, but possibly also with “Bouwer”, “Bouwen”, etc.

The good news is that Web Publications allow linking to external thesauri, synonym lists, spelling variation services or e.g. a diachronic lexicon.¹⁶

Our analysis is that high-quality (transcription) text, not the format, is the main facilitator of reliable search. Web Publications use web standards, which makes it easier to make them searchable and link (fragments of) them to search services.

4.3.4 Compare scan and text

When a user encounters errors in a recognized text, it might be very helpful to be able to view the scan and the text together – usually next to each other – and interpret what the text should have been. In some cases this comparison is easier, because the page is easy to find and the layout is similar enough to find the part of the image that corresponds with the text. In other cases this could be quite a challenge, especially if the layout or the text doesn’t match the layout of the (scan of the) original document.

Our analysis is that Web Publications facilitate the (e.g. next to each other) comparison of scan and text due to the concept of layers. This comparison is made easier when the layouts of the text and the scan match, but that is mostly a requirement for projects turning content into the format of Web Publications.

4.3.5 Improve text

Several users mentioned that not being able to improve the text is a problem. It is usually possible to make improvements in one’s own copy, but the fact that it is often not possible to share corrections is frustrating. It also means that text cleaning has to be done again and again by every user who obtains a copy from the original source (i.e. a library or archive). Of

course there is a question of responsibilities and trust in sharing corrections, but there are ways to organize this (like with Wikipedia.¹⁷ It is also understandable that for reproducibility of analysis it would be not acceptable if text would continuously change, but with proper versioning this could be covered.

NB Although seen as a problem area by users in our project, there are solutions available for (collaboratively) improving text. Various online applications (like website content management systems) allow the editing of HTML from a browser. Editing environments with version management are e.g. available in the form of Gitbook, Wikipedia and Google Docs. These functionalities 'only' have to be embedded in the library and archive services.

Our analysis is that the platform in which Web Publications are made available to users requires functionality for improving text.¹⁸

4.3.6 Adaptable presentation

People read less and for shorter periods of time.¹⁹ To make reading easier, digital text should be adaptable and e.g. 'flow' with the layout presented by the device used. Even with 'born digital' documents that contain no errors and look very crisp, users find it frustrating when they cannot optimize the presentation. For e-books this has been a long development and recently Adobe started the development of more flexible way to render PDF.²⁰ Users with a reading impairment have an even stronger need to adapt the presentation of documents, but the underlying principles are very similar. It is important to notice that there is an interplay between format and reading environment: without a consistent basic document structure a reading environment cannot render a document properly.

Our analysis is that Web Publications offer the (open web) features for implementing both fixed and 'flowing' layouts.

4.3.7 Reading text aloud

Reading text aloud is a requirement for people with an reading impairment. However, it could be used by many more people. One requirement for this is high quality text, such as proper sentences in the correct reading order. The same requirement is something that is also practical for other purposes, like text analysis.

NB WCAG compliant HTML it is possible to make the processing of special elements (such as foot notes) dependant on the user's preferences. This increases the user's appreciation of the experience.

Cloud services that provide narration are available and improving quickly. Of course, old languages and dialect will have its challenges.

Our analysis is that Web Publications lend themselves very well to storing structured text, which can then easily be automatically read aloud (e.g. via text-to-speech cloud services). The concept of layers also allows pre-recorded audio to be linked to and aligned with the text.

4.3.8 Explicit navigation structure

An explicit navigation structure, like a HTML Table of Contents element²¹, is much more practical than searching for the (often implicit) text pages that contain a text-based table of contents. In e-books it has become common practise to provide a ToC, but even in PDF we often notice only an index with thumbnails that is not so helpful. Also, for documents other than

books or reports, table of content information is less common. However, for quick navigation, 'outline views' that can expand and collapse, can tremendously improve usability (compared to browsing page by page).

Our analysis is that Web Publications have an explicit navigation structure, and are therefore well-suited to meet this requirement.

4.3.9 Reading and storing documents offline

While many archives offer possibilities to download copies of documents for offline usage, relationships with online resources are lacking. This means that if users work on a local file, there is no way to share improvements or annotations back to the repository where the original resides. One of the interesting aspects of the Web Publication concept, is to provide a means where these documents are connected. Like with e-books where annotations can be synchronised between instances on different devices, a presentation of digitised books where people can also collaborate instead of only consume, would offer new possibilities.

Our analysis is that Web Publications offer a means to maintain links between information from local (e.g. downloaded to the user's device) and remote (e.g. the original in the repository) versions of a resource.

4.3.10 Making annotations

The need to make annotations is centuries old. With digital text we still struggle to find a good way to do this. On the one hand it is easy to add an annotation to a document (users mentioned iAnnotate as a good example of how to annotate a PDF), but sharing annotations is more complex. Especially when one does not want an annotation linked to an image, but to a text fragment, it is important to agree on a structural approach. With Web Annotations a model was conceptualized, but so far this has not led to large-scale adoption. When documents do not have a fixed layout, and instead can be reflowed, it makes sense to use structural addressing like canonical fragment identifiers. However earlier attempts to introduce those have not led to wide use either.

Our analysis is that Web Publications cater for linking annotations to the text. But it does not provide a solution for making and sharing annotations. Web Annotations²² is a direction to look for a solution, but both formats need more standardization and use cases before a large-scale adoption will happen.

4.3.11 Granular citation

Users want to be able to create citations with a link to (a fragment within) a source document. For citations, just like with annotations, it is necessary to have agreements about fragment identifiers to link to. Unfortunately, there is no standard yet.

This wish would fit nicely with the following requirements from the Web Publication specification²³:

- Req. 4: A Web Publication, as a collection of resources, must be identified by either a single URL or a unique handle that can resolve to a single URL.
- Req. 5: All constituent resources, and their contents, should be identified by either a URL or a unique handle that can resolve to a URL.

Our analysis is that a (widely adopted) standard for fragment identifiers is required before granular citation can be made an integral part of Web Publications.

4.3.12 Perform text analysis

Assuming that the HTML text is well structured, it should be possible to do text analysis.²⁴ We know from practice that ePub documents sometimes contain very messily structured text, so that it was necessary to clean up the documents before any analysis was possible. With accessible HTML, this should be a lot better structured. Exactly what is required for 'good enough' text analysis is uncertain. The extent to which all the requirements for text analysis are met therefore deserves further investigation.

Our analysis is that Web Publications allow text to be structured, which is often a requirement for (advanced) text analysis. The extent to which text is of high quality and well-structured, and the extent to which a text is suitable for a particular type of text analysis is however not a feature of the format but of the publication's lifecycle.

4.3.13 Automatic translation

In our digital, globalised world, and with e.g. many foreign exchange students in the Netherlands²⁵, many users use information written in other languages than their native language. Translated texts, and being able to use automatic translation in search queries would support this, even if it would only be used to collect possibly interesting sources for further research.

Similar to automatically reading text out aloud, an explicit sentence structure is crucial for automatic translation. Now that there are high-quality online translation services available, and translation is often embedded in social media apps, automatic translation has become a commodity. Users will not accept awkward word-by-word translations of texts.

Our analysis is that Web Publications lend themselves very well to storing structured text, which can then easily be automatically translated (e.g. via translation cloud services). The concept of layers also allows canned translations to be linked to and aligned with the text.

4.3.14 Link fragments in related documents together

Not only for citation purposes, but also for linking fragments in related documents together, it is important to have a standard for fragment identifiers. Otherwise, it would be impossible to align e.g. a translated or audio version to the original. To a certain extent 'media overlays' in ePub documents provide this. A SMIL file²⁶ is used to store the relations between the HTML text and audio fragments.

Our analysis is that Web Publications lend themselves very well to linking fragments in related documents together. But as discussed under Making annotations and Granular citation, more standardization in the area of fragment identifiers is required.

4.4 Web Publication advantages

From the above, we can distill some general advantages of the Web Publications model:

- The open structure makes it possible to add additional components or layers (not necessarily on the same location), and to share them with others.

- The open structure makes it possible to maintain different versions of components without having to change the original source (similar to how Wikipedia and Gitbooks function)

4.5 Web Publication limitations

From the above 14 requirements and the discussion of each requirement, we can draw some general limitations of the current Web Publication model:

- Hierarchy: HTML enforces a certain order in information. The original documents don't always have or provide such an order. This makes it more difficult to create HTML versions of the original documents.
- Alignment: in paragraphs of text, the text alignment is often different from the alignment in the original document, making it more difficult to compare them. A fixed layout of the text helps, but is currently more expensive to make than the dynamic, 'flowing' layout of more standard HTML. It also requires more manual (alignment) work, limiting the scalability of solutions

- Standard HTML does not provide solutions for all types of elements encountered in digitized documents.

```
<?xml version="1.0">
<address>
<name>Lewis Carroll</name>
<contact>123456789</contact>
<email>lewiscarroll@gmail.com </email>
<birthdate>27-01-1832</birthdate>
</address>
```

XML Example

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Page title</title>
</head>
<body>
<h1>First Heading</h1>
<p>First paragraph.</p>
</body>
</html>
```

HTML Example

- There is not (enough) fragment identifier standardisation), making it harder to create annotations and link other media.

5

Cost-benefit analysis

5 Cost-benefit analysis²⁷

For this research, we wanted to gain insight on how individuals are using digitized materials, what their needs are, and if Web Publications could facilitate those needs. Therefore, as an addition to the user research and the demo, we undertook an exploratory cost-benefit analysis conducted by SEO Economisch Onderzoek (economic research). Since it is exploratory, the analysis looks at what costs and benefits can develop, and to which stakeholders these apply.

One thing that was established during the analysis were some of the current problems and how Web Publications offer possibilities to solve these. These problems are that documents are not properly searchable because of OCR mistakes, sharing documents is not possible, low accessibility for the visually impaired, and limited uses. Web Publications offer possibilities to work on these problems by e.g. having a possible flexible layout and offering possibilities to share documents.

The next step was to assess which stakeholders who could benefit from Web Publications. The following groups could for example benefit from Web Publications:

- Researchers (professional)
- Teachers and their students
- Journalists and their readers
- Visually impaired people
- Companies

For a more extensive, quantifiable cost-benefit analysis in the future we need to know more about the effects for users.

6

Further research

6 Further research

Our investigation of Web Publications resulted in answers, but it also raised new questions. We don't have answers to all the questions, but we have found places where to look for answers. In this chapter, we will discuss open research questions and where we think we can find answers, and partners to initiate new projects with.

6.1 How to change a digitized document into an accessible Web Publication

Work needs to be done on a workflow for changing a digitized document into an accessible Web Publication. Given that accessibility of web content is already more advanced than that of other formats, this was an important reason to look in this direction. However we also learned that currently a lot of manual work is needed to 'remediate' current content into an accessible web format. For the numbers of documents in our collections, this would quickly become unaffordable. However for certain sub-collections, that are already structured more 'semantically', we see possibilities. Like the current DBNL collection formatted in TEI XML.

For this a follow-up project is being planned in cooperation with the Future Libraries Lab of TU Delft.

6.2 How to make and share annotations

Our project, and also the IJsberg project mentioned before, showed that users are looking for ways to create and share, in some standardized form, annotations. Also, the societal attention for inclusivity and diversity, requires that libraries, archives and other cultural heritage organizations start to look for ways to include more perspectives to their collections. Allowing users to create and share annotations could be a step in the right direction. We already mentioned Web Annotations as a possible solution. NA, WAAG Society,²⁸ and CLARIAH have expressed their interest in doing more research in this area. We also discussed Social Reading with Bob Stein of the Institute for the Future of the Book.

6.3 How to change other non-book like documents into Web Publications

We included three documents in our demonstrator SamePage: Alice in Wonderland, Max Havelaar and one document from a collection of notarial deeds of notaries (notariële akten van notarissen) from the IJsberg project. The first two documents are real books. The third could be considered book alike. However our collections also contain documents like newspapers, spreadsheets, maps and photos. To turn in a Web Publication, we will need additional structure definitions.

There are no leads for working on this research question, mostly because there first needs to be a scalable, affordable workflow in place for book-like documents (see paragraph 1). Then we can start to answer this more advanced issue. It will help that we have contacts within W3C for cooperation.

6.4 How to provide access to restricted material

Web Publications do not have any copyright protection or privacy regulation implementations yet, but we want to mention the issue here, because the users we interviewed brought this up. Copyrights or privacy regulations often restrict access to material, and therefore many documents cannot be made available online. We expect that with other web developments, which are compatible with Web Publications, these issues might be addressed sooner, then with proprietary formats.

6.5 How to make access to collections more intuitive

If we want to attract a broader audience, we should make our services much more intuitive and usable for this broader audience. Our current users (mostly researchers) usually have more background knowledge and are used to more advanced (not so intuitive) research environments. The researcher will know how to use indexes and work with the archival description system, or will be willing to learn to use them. The general public is used to easy to use consumer orientated tools and will expect to get access to digitized material in a similar manner.

Turning digitized content into Web Publications, could help to make the user experience more intuitive and attractive. But only in combination with the text quality and an improved reading environment.

If Web Publications allow users to help with improving text, an improved text quality will lead to better search results (with less necessity to learn about regular expressions and other technically advanced search methods)

If Web Publications are structured more semantically, it will be easier to search for text parts (like articles) without becoming a search expert first.

SENDS

at Alice, and, after
heard the Rabbit
suddenly spread
out her hand, and
made a snatch in the
air. She did not get
hold of anything, but
she heard a little
rattle and a fall,
and a crash of bro-
ken glass, from which
she concluded that
it was just possible
she had fallen into a
rabbit-hole, or
something of the sort.

Rabbit's—
and then a
"Sure then
out!"
said the
help me

waiting till she fancied she heard
just under the window, she su-

out, h
made a
air. S
hold of
she hea
shriek
and a cr
ken glass,
she concl
it was ju
it had fall
cucumber-
something o

Next came an angry voice—the R
"Pat! Pat! Where are you?" And
voice she had never heard before, "Su
I'm here! Digging for apples, yer honour
Rabbit angrily. "Here! Come and hel
out of this!" (Sounds of more broken glas

Conclusion

7 Conclusion

From the first phase of this research, we concluded that users indeed have needs and wishes that are hard to address with current document formats. These formats work reasonable well for retrieval, but not for collaboration and tasks that require advanced language processing. For themes like accessibility, collaborative quality improvement and enrichment, we need different structures.

In the second phase, the development of a demonstrator, we experimented with 'Web Publication alike' structures, to see if these could address user's needs. Though some standards (HTML) are too rigid, and others (Web Annotations) not mature enough, we found the concept of Web Publications promising. A significant advantage is the open structure, which makes it possible to maintain versions of different document components. Restructuring text into elements that match 'semantic' models, make it possible to adapt document presentation to the preferences of the user, which could vary from better display on mobile screens to automatic narration. Even comparison between two similar (but not identical) document versions and automatic translation become much more feasible. The same structures provide a practical foundation for collaboration, with examples like collaborative correction of OCR errors, sharing annotations and linking quotations to other (web-)resources.

Given the state of Web Publication technology, a quick large scale implementation is not conceivable. However the insights give direction to further research, in both organizations as well in collaboration with other institutions. Themes like accessibility, large scale content analysis with AI, providing (diversity of) context to content, all demand higher-level structures. We need to set standards for these and (re-)structure existing content into these formats, if we want to facilitate our users well.

Footnotes

- 1 <https://www.w3.org/TR/pwp/>
- 2 <https://www.w3.org/TR/pwp/>
- 3 <https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>
- 4 <http://www.loc.gov/standards/alto/>
- 5 <https://www.primaresearch.org/tools/PAGELibraries>
- 6 <http://kba.cloud/hocr-spec/1.2/>
- 7 https://www.pdfa.org/norm-refs/warnock_camelot.pdf
- 8 <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/pdf-unfit-for-human-consumption/>
- 9 For the complete report on the user research, see: ...
- 10 With webdocs we mean digitized materials made available on the web.
- 11 The initial demonstrator can be found at: <https://vanleeuwen.studio/demonstrator/>. The final demonstrator, named SamePage, can be found at: <https://app.samepagedemo.com>
- 12 <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/over-het-na/datalab-nationaal-archief/handschrift-herkenning>
- 13 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Project_Jupyter#Jupyter_Notebook
- 14 <https://www.clariah.nl/>
- 15 Smith, David A. and Ryan Cordell. 'A Research Agenda for Historical and Multilingual Optical Character Recognition'. Northeastern University. <http://hdl.handle.net/2047/D20298542>
- 16 Such as <https://ivdnt.org/corpora-lexica/diamant/>.
- 17 See e.g. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:About#Contributors>
- 18 See also 4.3.10: Making annotations.
- 19 <https://www.kb.nl/ob-kb/nieuws/2018/minder-lezen-maar-nog-steeds-veel-papier> (Dutch).
- 20 <https://blog.adobe.com/en/fpost/2020/reimagining-reading-infographic.html>
- 21 <https://www.w3.org/TR/wpub/#table-of-contents>, ToC
- 22 <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>
- 23 [w3.org/TR/pwp-ucr/](https://www.w3.org/TR/pwp-ucr/)
- 24 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Text_mining
- 25 <https://www.volkskrant.nl/nieuws-achtergrond/aantal-buitenlandse-studenten-van-buiten-de-eu-dat-naar-nederland-komt-weer-vanouds-hoog-becc2194/>
- 26 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Synchronized_Multimedia_Integration_Language
- 27 The report of the cost-benefit analysis (Dutch) can be found via: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5785272>
- 28 <https://waag.org/>